

Spectrophotometric Determination of the Thermodynamic Ionisation Constant of 3,5-Dinitrobenzoic Acid in Water from 10° to 50° and Related Thermodynamic Quantities

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The thermodynamic ionisation constant (K_a) of 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid in water from 10° to 50° has been investigated spectrophotometrically. The results are shown as a function of temperature (T) in °K by $pK_a = -1147.0/T + 6.9381 - 9.933 \times 10^{-4} T$. The changes of free energy (ΔF), enthalpy (ΔH), entropy (ΔS), and heat capacity (ΔC_p) for the dissociation process have been calculated from the temperature coefficient of the dissociation constant. The equations relating these thermodynamic functions with absolute temperature are also given. The ' pK_a ' of the acid increases linearly with increase in ionic strength of the buffer solution and can be related by the equation $pK_a = 2.0297 I + 2.9255$ up to an ionic strength (I) of 0.1. The values of K_a have also been found out for various methanol-water mixtures.

In a previous communication, Gupta *et al.*¹ reported the determination at 303.45°K of the thermodynamic ionisation constant (K_a) of 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid in water, which is in use to characterise the alcohols. These studies have now been extended to the determination of ' K_a ' at different temperatures in the range of 283.16° to 323.16° K and of the related thermodynamic quantities like change in free energy, entropy, etc. on which no data exist in the literature. The effect of ionic strength has been studied and the value of K_a has also been determined in various methanol-water mixtures.

EXPERIMENTAL

A recrystallised B. D. H. sample of 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid was used. Methanol was of B. D. H., A. R. quality and was redistilled in an all-glass fractionating system and the middle one-third of the distillate was used for experiments. Potassium chloride (B. D. H., A. R.) was used for maintaining different ionic strengths. The other chemicals used for preparing acid standard, base standard, and buffer solutions were of AnalaR quality of B. D. H. Conductivity water was used for preparing solutions.

A Hilger Uvispec spectrophotometer, model H700.308, having 1 cm effective light path, was used for studying the absorption spectra over a temperature range of 10° to 50°. The cell compartment was fitted with a jacket through which water could be circulated from a thermostat (Townson and Mercer Ltd., England). A thermometer, inserted into the cell compartment and allowed to come to temperature equilibrium, showed a variation of less than 0.1° over periods of time much longer than those needed to make measurements of optical density. Absorption of the acid was determined in (a) 0.1M-HCl, (b) a buffer containing sodium acetate (1.25 ml of 0.1M) and acetic acid (23.75 ml of 0.1M), and (c) 0.1M-NaOH. Beckman pH-meter (model H2) was used for pH measurements.

TABLE I

Effect of ionic strength on the dissociation of 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid.

Ionic strength.	pK_a (obs.)	pK_a (calc.)*
0.0050	2.94	2.95
0.0150	2.96	2.98
0.0500	3.01	3.03
0.0800	3.08	3.09
0.1000	3.13	3.13

$$*pK_a = 2.0297 I + 2.9255.$$

TABLE II

Determination of dissociation constant of 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid at diff. temp.

Temp.	pK_a (obs.)	pK_a (calc.) ^a .
283.16°K	2.60	2.60
293.16°	2.73	2.73
303.16°	2.85	2.85
313.16°	2.96	2.96
323.16°	3.07	3.07

$$*pK_a = -1147.0/T + 6.9361 - 0.006933 T.$$

TABLE III

Thermodynamic functions for the dissociation of 3, 5-dinitrobenzoic acid from 10° to 50°.

Temp.	$\Delta F.$ (j.mole ⁻¹).	$\Delta H.$ (j.mole ⁻¹).	$\Delta S.$ (j. deg. ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹).	$\Delta C_p.$ (j.deg ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹).
283.16°K	14124	-17743	-112.6	-125.3
293.16°	15348	-19019	-117.2	-129.7
303.16°	16571	-20338	-121.8	-134.1
313.16°	17754	-21702	-126.0	-138.6
323.16°	18982	-23115	-130.3	-143.0

DISCUSSION

The ionisation constant K_o is expressed by the equation

$$pK_o = pH + \log \frac{b-e}{e-a} \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

where the pH is that of the buffer solution of the acid having absorbance 'e' and 'a' and 'b' are the absorbances of the same concentration of the acid in acid and base standards, respectively. Further, the value of the thermodynamic ionisation constant (K_o) may be calculated by the equation^a

$$pK_a = pK_o + \frac{I^{\frac{1}{2}}}{1 + I^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad \dots \quad (ii)$$

where 'I' is the ionic strength of the buffer solution. The values of pK_o were measured within the wave lengths 370 to 425 $m\mu$ with an interval of 5 $m\mu$ and were found to be constant within the limits of ± 0.1 unit of pK_o . The average value of pK_o , thus obtained, was used for calculation of pK_a .

Table I records the values of pK_a at various ionic strengths of the buffer solution. It can be seen that ' pK_a ' increases or ' K_a ' decreases with increase in ionic strength. This increase in pK_a with ionic strength is linear and could be expressed by the equation:

$$pK_a = 2.0297I + 2.9255 \quad \dots \quad (iii)$$

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up to a ionic strength of 0.1, where 'I' has the usual significance. The calculated values of ' pK_a ' by the equation are shown in the third column showing good agreement with the values of pK_a obtained in the second column of Table I. The increase in pK_a with increase of ionic strength is due to the lowering of the activity coefficient of the ionic species with increase of ionic strength. The value of the pK_a at zero ionic strength can thus be computed by extrapolation of the linear curve to zero ionic strength and it comes out to be 2.9255 at 303.16°K.

Table II records the values of pK_a at different temperatures. The results in this table show that pK_a increases with increase in temperature and the corresponding values could be expressed by the equation:

$$pK_a = -A/T + B - CT \quad \dots \quad (iv)$$

where A , B , and C are constants with the following values: $A = 1147.0$; $B = 6.9381$; $C = 9.933 \times 10^{-4}$.

The values of pK_a , calculated from the above equation, are recorded in the third column which agree well with the observed values (second column) in Table II. The fact that $\delta(\Delta F)/\delta T$, i.e. the temperature coefficient of the free energy change (vide Table III), is positive and that enthalpy change (ΔH) is negative (vide Table III) indicates that the dissociation of the acid in water is an exothermic process. The value of K_a , which also represents the equilibrium constant, therefore decreases with increase of temperature. The decrease of K_a with increase of temperature may also be related to the dielectric constant of the medium which decreases with increase in temperature³.

From equation (iv) are obtained the values of the change of free energy (ΔF), heat content (ΔH), entropy (ΔS), and heat capacity (ΔC_p) of the dissociation of 3, 5-dinitrobenzoic acid. These are recorded in Table III. All the thermodynamic functions shown in this table increase in magnitude (with sign) linearly with increase of temperature. These relations can be expressed by the equations:

$$\Delta F = -24382.064 + 148.7335 T - 0.045T^2 \text{ j. mole}^{-1} \quad \dots \quad (v)$$

$$\Delta H = 17.55185 - 0.22150 T^2 \text{ j. mole}^{-1} \quad \dots \quad (vi)$$

$$\Delta S = 12.88545 - 0.4430 T \text{ j. deg.}^{-1} \text{ mole}^{-1} \quad \dots \quad (vii)$$

$$\Delta C_p = -0.44251T \text{ j. deg.}^{-1} \text{ mole}^{-1} \quad \dots \quad (viii)$$

These equations are valid from $T = 283.16^\circ \text{K}$ to $T = 323.16^\circ \text{K}$. The limits of deviations between the observed and the calculated values of these thermodynamic functions are as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta F &= \pm 13 \text{ j. mole}^{-1}; \quad \Delta H = \pm 4.0 \text{ j. mole}^{-1}; \\ \Delta S &= \pm 0.14 \text{ j. deg.}^{-1} \text{ mole}^{-1}; \quad \Delta C_p = \pm 0.02 \text{ j. deg.}^{-1} \text{ mole}^{-1}. \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 1 shows the nature of the curve obtained by plotting ' K_a ' vs. different compositions of the methanol-water mixtures.

FIG. 1

The value of K_a decreases rapidly up to a concentration of 40% methanol in the mixture, but concentrations greater than this produce slow decrease in the value of K_a . This is related to the decrease of the dielectric constant of the medium by increasing the percentage of methanol in the mixture. The decrease in the extent of solvation of the ionic species by increasing the concentration of methanol in the mixture may also have some influence in decreasing the value of K_a .

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